

PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED LANGUAGE'S TEACHING FOR THE SPECIALISTS IN THE FIELD OF MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT

In the face of the newly approved professional standards for medical specialists university teachers of foreign language are expected to teach students to fulfill their job functions and solve professional problems using communicative skills and competences determined in the Federal State Educational Standards. Moreover, teachers are expected to meet the needs of all students, supporting their autonomy and moving them toward fulfillment of their individual potential. Based on a review of research, theory, and current practices of teaching English for medical students, this paper emphasizes the autonomy-oriented approach to the educational process organization. In the context of teaching Medical English, the autonomy-oriented approach means personalisation of the educational process through the use of a complex of educational practices. In the framework of the autonomy-oriented approach, we determined conditions which are able to ensure a new type of profession-focused foreign language teaching.

Introduction

Among the transformations that have taken place in recent years in higher medical education, a special place is occupied by the problem of transformation in understanding the essence and role of the discipline "Foreign Language" in the professional training of graduates of medical universities. Today, from the category of a "secondary" subject for most students of non-linguistic universities, which involves the study of the system of a particular language, a foreign language is moving into the category of disciplines that determine the success of advancement in the profession, and becomes a means of personal and professional self-development of specialists.

The foregoing actualizes the problem of developing new approaches that provide such a type of professionalization of teaching a foreign language, in which language teaching will contribute to the effective performance of a number of labor functions by medical specialists.

Main part

In accordance with the identified problem, the purpose of the study was to identify and specify the skills that most fully meet modern medical and pharmaceutical practice (and, accordingly, reflected in professional standards), formed within the framework of language disciplines in medical and pharmaceutical universities, as well as setting new tasks for language training and identification of methods and means of their solution adequate to these tasks in the modern educational context.

Practically all professional standards include a section on sanitary and hygienic education, the formation of a healthy lifestyle among the population. This section is closely related to language competencies, without which a medical practitioner is unlikely to be able to successfully form patients' motivation to lead a healthy lifestyle.

The idea of professional development of a specialist, advanced training through participation in scientific and practical conferences, internships, which in the modern world often requires knowledge of a foreign language, runs like a red thread through professional standards (see, for example, the standard "Specialist in Pediatrics").

The standards of professional activity also focus on such types of work closely related to language competence as informing and counseling the patient, teaching him how to use medical equipment (in particular, the standard "Specialist in the field of hearing aids"). The degree of professionalization of language training can be increased by constantly reviewing the content of teaching the discipline "Foreign Language" by the teacher, which at various stages of preparation may include a discussion of professional plans and prospects, the content of the future profession, the image of a professional, motives for professional choice, professional values.

Following an autonomously oriented approach in teaching a foreign language to medical students, it is important to develop in students not only the skills of translating special medical texts, but also the skills of working with various machine translation systems (taking into account their advantages and disadvantages). In the field of writing, it is important to focus on the features of e-mail correspondence, on the requirements for the preparation of scientific articles in foreign journals. In the field of reading - on the structure and strategies of working with professional foreign language texts (scientific articles, electronic databases, websites). In the field of oral speech, it is necessary to prepare students for presentations and discussions of scientific reports, business information in a foreign language in a multicultural and multilingual audience.

Conclusion

Thus, responding to the challenges caused by the emergence of professional standards, an autonomously oriented approach allows for the transition from teaching medical students a foreign language to their self-determined continuous personal and professional development using a foreign language.

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